

MUSICAL PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND ITS PLACE IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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The changes being made in the education system of independent Uzbekistan are, of course, important in preparing the younger generation for the future of the country. Improving the quality of education, arming young people with modern knowledge and developing their critical thinking skills are one of the most urgent tasks today.

The Law "On Education", adopted in 2020, has strengthened the legal basis for reforms in the field of education and paved the way for innovations in all aspects of the education system. The changes being made in the education system of independent Uzbekistan are, of course, important in preparing the younger generation for the future of the country. Improving the quality of education, arming young people with modern knowledge and developing their critical thinking skills are one of the most urgent tasks today.

The Law "On Education", adopted in 2020, has strengthened the legal basis for reforms in the field of education and paved the way for innovations in all aspects of the education system. This law aims to make educational processes more democratic and transparent, take into account the individual needs of students, and improve the quality of pedagogical activities.

Providing young people with knowledge and skills at the level of modern requirements, encouraging them to think creatively, and directing them to a sense of social responsibility is the task of every specialist. It is also important to develop independent thinking and critical decision-making skills in young people, as well as to encourage them to come up with innovative ideas. Thus, today's reforms in the field of education serve not only to impart theoretical knowledge, but also to develop practical skills. This, in turn, will be a key factor in preparing responsible and resourceful specialists for the future of our country. This law aims to make educational processes more democratic and transparent, take into account the individual needs of students, and improve the quality of pedagogical activity. Providing young people with knowledge and skills at the level of modern requirements, encouraging them to think creatively, and directing them to a sense of social responsibility is the task of every specialist. It is also important to develop independent thinking and critical decision-making skills in young people, as well as to encourage them to come up

with innovative ideas. Thus, today's reforms in the field of education serve not only to impart theoretical knowledge, but also to develop practical skills. This, in turn, will be a key factor in preparing responsible and resourceful specialists for the future of our country.

It is aimed at forming a new generation of personnel, prepared on the basis of world-class achievements in the education system and possessing high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, the ability to independently set goals in socio-political life, capable of promoting and solving future tasks.

A start has been made to ensure a high quality indicator of the effectiveness of education, to improve the content of education on the basis of State Educational Standards. Monitoring is being carried out at the school, district, city, and republican levels to apply State Educational Standards in all academic subjects in the educational process and determine the compliance of the knowledge mastered by students with these standards at the end of the academic year.

As envisaged in the national program, the provision of information to the educational process is being developed on the basis of modern information technologies and computer networks. The publishing base of science and education is being developed. Educational - methodological, scientific, innovative, modern technologies are being improved and implemented in the educational process.

As is known, the subject of didactics is teaching, learning, and educational content. The three components involved in this are inextricably linked, and none of them can be ignored.

When we start with learning or teaching, the question naturally arises of what (what content of educational material) we want to learn or teach.

Both teaching and learning and their final result depend on the content of education.

Since it is accepted to master texts of various contents in specific ways, the nature of teaching depends on its content, which depends on the organizer of learning, that is, the teacher.

In short, didactic thinking means searching for and identifying constant connections and relationships between learning, teaching, and educational content.

The teacher seeks ways, methods and styles, teaching forms, methods and situations that activate students, are convenient for him and the student, and,

relying on modern pedagogical technology, increases the effectiveness of the educational process. By teaching students to think independently, he achieves high quality and efficiency of the educational process.

For this reason, pedagogical technology, didactic technology, educational technologies are considered the most effective tools in the educational process. They are widely used in world pedagogical practice.

The most urgent issue and task today is the implementation of educational standards in the educational process.

If this task is not implemented, the issues of achieving quality and efficiency in the field of education and upbringing, improving the educational process will remain unresolved.

- Pedagogical technology currently forms the basis of all pedagogical professions and professions related to the organization, management, and control of the educational process. All educators should be aware of modern pedagogical technologies. As the content, goals, and objectives of education and upbringing expand over time, its forms and methods are also improving. Currently, the main areas of human activity are turning into a holistic system, that is, technologies, that allow the full implementation of the goals set by this activity. Similarly, in the field of education, pedagogical technology has begun to be used in recent years.

The concept of pedagogical technology emerged in the 20th century and has been going through various stages of development.

From the mid-1950s to the 1960s, the term "educational technology" was used, which meant programmed education.

In the 1970s, the term "pedagogical technology" was used, which meant a previously designed and clearly defined educational process that guarantees the achievement of specific goals.

Since the beginning of the 1980s, pedagogical technology has been used to refer to the creation of computer and information technologies in education.

Definitions of pedagogical technology:

"Pedagogical technology is the activity of forming a well-rounded person."

At the same time, taking into account that pedagogical technology is a broad and multifaceted concept, we can give several more definitions of it:

Pedagogical technology consists of the process of learning to master information, use it in practice, and create new information by discovering new meanings and contents in it and various connections between information.

Pedagogical technology is a set of educational methods, methods, ways and educational tools; it is a set of organizational and methodological tools of the pedagogical process.

Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical resources and human relationships, which sets itself the task of optimizing forms of education.

Pedagogical technology is the process of transmitting and mastering information in a form and method convenient for mastering.

Thus, pedagogical technology consists of the activity of influencing a person (a learner) for a predetermined purpose.

Pedagogical technology is a process that guarantees the training of a student to independently study, acquire knowledge, and think.

In the process of pedagogical technology, a student independently receives, learns, and masters knowledge under the guidance of a teacher.

Based on the principles of democratization, individualization of education, and taking into account regional characteristics, a teaching concept has been developed for all subjects, including music. The subject of musical culture serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to implement the education of national pride and patriotism, to develop creative skills, refinement and artistic taste, to expand the scope of thought, to educate independence and initiative. The subject of musical culture is connected with all subjects taught in general secondary schools, including literature, fine arts, physical education, labor and other subjects. The introduction of DTS in music education, along with all subjects, allows for the full use of national musical heritage. These are reflected in practical folk melodies and songs, the creative activities of singers and musicians. Maqom, shashmakom epics and today's modern music. Such opportunities of musical art serve as a unique and unique source in the upbringing of the new generation, their harmonious development. From time immemorial, the pedagogy of music education and upbringing has been improving on the example of the East, including the Uzbek, and its excellent traditions of teacher and student. State educational standards standardize the study of the elementary foundations of mass folk music pedagogy, professional music creators, music performers (musicians, singers), great singers, maqomists, and dostoniks. The new educational content based on the State Educational Standards in music education, along with the musical knowledge and skills of students, ensures the development of such qualities as observation,

memory strengthening, figurative imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. The new content of musical culture education involves raising the younger generation to the level of a cultured person who can inherit our national musical heritage, who can perceive the universal, riches of music. The main goal is for students to study the art of music with all its grace, to engage in mass musical activities: artistic perception of music, singing individually and in groups, dancing, and the formation of creative skills. In addition, the main task of music education is to develop students' musical talent, increase love and passion for the art of music, create the necessary conditions for the development of the talent of students interested in the art of music, and satisfy their artistic needs. At the same time, in-depth study of the universal musical values of the peoples of the world ensures that the younger generation enjoys cultural masterpieces that have a tendency to international influence.

The development of society never stops, its wheel always turns forward, this is a natural, historical process. Therefore, a teacher of musical culture should systematically form students' spiritual, artistic and moral culture, educate national pride and patriotism, cultivate creative skills, refinement, artistic taste, expand the circle of thought, and form independence and initiative. We know that pedagogy, as a science of education, involves understanding the essence of education, revealing its laws and thereby influencing the educational process of human interests.

The first of the pedagogical skills of a teacher of musical culture should be to study the translations gained in the field of education. This, of course, will help in solving many problems.

Along with the experience of advanced teachers, the activities of ordinary teachers are also studied. Because the problem in the process of studying experiences is to identify achievements and shortcomings. In this, observation, interviewing, questionnaires, studying students' written and creative works, pedagogical documents are used, for example: during observation, a pedagogical phenomenon to be studied is recorded with a specific purpose. This process is carried out on the basis of a clear plan.

The interview is conducted to clarify the materials collected during the collection of facts - evidence or observation. "The interview is used as an independent or auxiliary method."

Questionnaires are carried out to collect material. A skilled teacher, like all students, must study school documents. This includes being aware of the

personal files of teachers, methodologist's reports, diaries, meeting minutes. He also conducts extracurricular music club activities. For example: In ancient Greece, it was believed that wisdom and courage can be cultivated with the help of music. In fact, every art has a spiritual effect on a person. Music has a great power in emotional influence. Therefore, music is widely used in many countries in many areas.

In the current theory and practice of school activities, there are many options for implementing new ways of implementing and conducting the educational process. Each author and practitioner adds his own individual contribution to the pedagogical process. However, many new technologies have enough similarities in their goals, content, methods and means of application that they are classified according to these common features.

- by the level of application;
- by the philosophical basis;
- by the main developing factor;
- by the concept of mastery;
- by the orientation towards the qualities of a personal character
- by the characteristics of the content;
- by the type of management;
- by the approach to the child;
- by the most commonly used methods;
- by the categories of learners.

Based on the above classification, as an example, the current traditional school education can be classified as follows.

- by the level of application: general pedagogical;
- by the philosophical basis; compulsory pedagogy
(general compulsory education)
- by the main developmental factor: the main focus is on educating well-rounded people who are active members of society; at the same time, attention is paid to the all-round development of the individual;
- by the concept of mastery; associative - reflective, relying on (example, example, role model).
- by orientation according to the qualities of the individual, informative, that is, aimed at the formation and strengthening of knowledge, skills, abilities;
- by content characteristics: secular, technocratic, in the content of general education, didactics is given a central place in the organization and conduct of the educational process;

- by type of management: traditional-classical (classical), with the addition of technical means of education;
- by approach to the child: authoritarian;
- by the most commonly used methods: explanatory-illustrative;
- by the categories of learners: mass.

At the same time, the development of society in individual countries and in the world as a whole has created new pedagogical technologies based on a humanistic philosophical basis.

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